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Report on **Milestone 22**

Inventory of computing space needed for processing and analysing accelerometer data

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Abstract:

This report documents the achievement of the Milestone 22 of the SSHOC project, which was to evaluate the feasibility and technical requirements to handle and perform analysis on accelerometer data in large studies. The two main challenges on data transfer and data preparation were identified and successfully addressed. Though the processing takes a significant amount of time and the implementation is cumbersome, it is feasible to do the data processing with standard office computers.

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1. Introduction

Measures of physical activity based on sensor data are more reliable and comparable than self-reported assessments of activity (cf. Gupta et al; Prince et al). With devices becoming affordable and analysing techniques more sophisticated, the use of accelerometers in large surveys is a valuable method to collect data. Accelerometer data provide information on physical activity, which is highly relevant for health research. To track movements, the acceleration is recorded by the device multiple times per second. This results in a huge amount of raw sensor data. The detailed information is useful for analysis; however, it comes along with high requirements concerning storage space and computing power. The aim of this milestone was to evaluate the feasibility and technical requirements to handle and perform analysis on accelerometer data in large studies such as the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE).

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1. Role of the Milestone

In the SHARE accelerometer study, respondents were instructed to wear the device at the thigh for eight consecutive days. The device recorded the acceleration for three axis with a frequency of 50 Hz. This results in a huge amount of raw sensor data that has to be handled and processed before making it available for

secondary data analyses. This report describes two internal steps and technical requirements of processing the data, that are both necessary for the final goal of the data release.

The first technical challenge is *data transfer*. As the SHARE data collection is conducted by survey agencies, a reliable, secure, and easy method was developed to transfer the raw sensor data from the survey agencies in the ten participating countries to SHARE Central and the data archive at CentERdata. This was achieved with the tool “Device CTRL” developed by CentERdata.

The second step is appropriate *data processing and preparation*. The raw sensor data is only usable with specialised programs that require knowledge in the functionality of accelerometers. Accelerometers are mainly used in medicine, sport science and public health intervention programmes, but not yet very common in social sciences. To make the accelerometer data more accessible and understandable for researchers in disciplines in which the use of sensor measured physical activity is not yet common, SHARE wants to provide easy to use generated variables to the research community. This means that analyses are performed by the data provider before the data is released.

Both steps are relevant for survey experts and future studies that plan to conduct an accelerometer measurement. The data transfer and availability of information from the field is especially important in settings where many parties are involved, e.g. an international study like SHARE with different survey agencies operating at the same time. In line with the open science principles that SSHOC follows, the procedures for processing and analysing accelerometer data were developed based on open source software that is available to the whole survey community. Source code of the newly developed software (CaseCNTRL) will be published and openly available according to the SSHOC standards and requirements.

2.2. Means of verification

According to the SSHOC Description of Action, the means of verification is availability of the overview calculation table. The procedure was tested with two different computer settings with high computing power (details below). As the inventory of computing spaces needed for processing and analysing accelerometer data required less specification than expected, all details are described in the following text and not in a table. The main results are that no substantial differences across the computer settings were observed, therefore no further detailed estimations were required to conclude.

To transfer the raw sensor files from the survey agencies to SHARE Central a tool was developed by CentERdata. Device CTRL is a database that combines all functionalities needed for handling the accelerometer data and monitoring the fieldwork. Survey agencies can enter all information on devices and respondents (e.g., assignments of devices and participants, dates of shipment of devices, wearing time, etc.) as well as upload the data files. Device CTRL offers an easy-to-use front end for survey agencies that can be accessed via standard internet browsers. SHARE Central can download the database and files anytime during fieldwork. Device CTRL also reports live statistics e.g., number of devices in the field and number of uploaded data files. Device CTRL is written in PHP. It uses a MySQL Server 5.7 database run on an Apache HTTP server that enables secure data

transmission by communicating with HTTPS. As the size of a raw sensor data file (for one participant) is about 300 to 500 megabytes¹, a server with sufficient storage space is needed.

For the processing of the accelerometer data, i.e., the analysis to generate easy to use aggregated variables, not only storage space but also high computing capacity is necessary. The procedure in SHARE is based on the software package GGIR for Raw Accelerometer Data Analysis (Migueles et al. 2019), an open-source package for the statistical software R. It is combined with additional processing steps using Stata to fit in the overall SHARE data processing structure. The time-consuming part of the GGIR procedure is the import and processing of the (large) raw sensor data. The duration of the processing step depends on the settings, e.g. on the selection of measures calculated, and optional features such as imputation for non-wear time and export of csv files.

GGIR offers the possibility to use multi-core processing if at least 4 CPU cores are available. On a system with a multi-core processor (Intel Xeon CPU E3-1286 v3 @ 3.70GHz) and sufficient working memory (32 GB RAM) the data processing takes approx. 35 to 40 hours for 100 raw data files.² To reduce the processing time, it is possible to run GGIR on a computing cluster. However, it depends on the amount of accelerometer data and how often the processing is executed whether it is worth the effort to become acquainted with programming of cluster computing.

A time-consuming data processing may not be a major problem for the data provider, since the step of data processing is only necessary once if the settings are fixed. However, it is possible that the processing step will be repeated in the future, e.g. due to software updates or changed preferences in the settings.

3. Conclusions and next steps

For both of the two main issues concerning technical requirements of the SHARE accelerometer study a satisfying solution was elaborated. Data transfer during fieldwork via the Device CTRL tool by CentERdata worked satisfactorily. The online tool was available without major interruptions or technical problems and ensured a secure transfer.

¹ In SHARE, the accelerometer raw data files are quite large due to the procedure used. The device records acceleration before and after wear time (starting with the configuration of the device) because the respondent should not be bothered with the handling of the device (turn it on/off).

² The long processing time also results from the method used in SHARE that leads to large raw sensor files including a lot of non-wear time data, see footnote 1.

Although it is time-consuming, the data processing is feasible with standard office computers. Setting up the procedure is cumbersome, especially in the initial stage with a lot of back-and-forth testing of settings. However, for the SHARE accelerometer project, there was no need for a computing cluster-based routine. The data processing of the SHARE accelerometer study is on track. The generated variables are subject to tests and will be presumably available for release in 2021.

4. References

- Gupta N., Christiansen C.S., Hanisch C., Bay H., Burr H., Holtermann A. (2017). Is questionnaire-based sitting time inaccurate and can it be improved? A cross-sectional investigation using accelerometer-based sitting time, *BMJ Open*. 7:e013251, doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013251
- Migueles, J. H., Rowlands, A. V., Huber, F., Sabia, S., & van Hees, V. T. (2019). GGIR: A Research Community-Driven Open Source R Package for Generating Physical Activity and Sleep Outcomes From Multi-Day Raw Accelerometer Data, *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 2(3), 188-196, doi: 10.1123/jmpb.2018-0063
- Prince S.A., Adamo K.B., Hamel M.E., Hardt J., Connor Gorber S., Tremblay M. (2008). A comparison of direct versus self-report measures for assessing physical activity in adults: a systematic review, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 5(56), doi: 10.1186/1479-5868-5-56